

Socio-Demographic Correlates Of Birth Preparedness And Complication Readiness Among Pregnant Women Attending Antenatal Clinic In South East Senatorial District Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the socio-demographic correlates of birth preparedness and complication readiness among pregnant women in South-East Senatorial District, Rivers State. A descriptive correlational research design was adopted with a population consisting 1,965 women attending ante-natal clinic in South East senatorial district of Rivers State. The sample size was 983 which was selected using a multi-stage sampling procedure. Data was collected using structured questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.81. Data collected were analyzed with the aid of the Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS V-23) using the Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of this study revealed that there was a significant relationship between birth preparedness and complication readiness and socio-demographic factors such as family income level (n = 969; r = 0.26; p<0.05); parity (n = 969; r = 0.28; p<0.05); maternal educational status (n = 969; r = 0.13; p<0.05), and knowledge of obstetric emergency signs (n = 969; r = 0.77; p<0.05). In conclusion, birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women in South-East Senatorial District, Rivers State was correlated with the socio-demographic factors of women such as family income level, parity, maternal educational status and knowledge of obstetric emergency signs. It was recommended that, health educators in collaboration with nurses and midwives should enhance women's knowledge of obstetric emergency by visiting antenatal clinics at regular intervals to remind women on the need for adequate birth preparedness.

Keywords: Correlates, Demographic, Preparedness, South East

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, more women of reproductive age die annually from complications associated with pregnancy and childbirth. Annually, childbirth complication contributes to 115,000 maternal deaths, and 99% of this mortality transpires in low-resource settings. More than half of these deaths occur within the first 24 hours following childbirth and are associated with profuse bleeding (Halle-Ekane et al., 2016). Maternal mortality remains a paramount global health problem, mainly in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) where more than 50 % of maternal deaths occurred. Nigeria's 58,000 maternal deaths accounts for 19% of global maternal mortality rate (WHO, 2018). Poor birth preparedness and complication readiness can contribute to delivery-related maternal mortality.

Birth preparedness and complication readiness has several components. The components of birth preparedness and complication readiness as highlighted by World Health Organization (2014) are: plan

for where to give birth, plan for skilled birth attendant, plan for transportation, provision of birth companion, identification of compatible blood donors in case of emergency, and registration of pregnancy through antenatal care. The correlates of birth preparedness are those factors that trigger or facilitate health seeking behavior among pregnant women. Dahab and Sakellariou (2020) identified such contributing factors poverty, long distance to health facilities, inadequate information, and lack of education, poor quality of services, cultural beliefs and practice. Such factors are conceptualized as knowledge of obstetric emergency signs, family income level, educational status and parity.

The parity or the number of previous children a woman has experienced is a crucial correlate that significantly shapes birth preparedness. The maternal experiences and knowledge gained from previous childbirths play a pivotal role in influencing a woman's approach to birth planning, recognition of danger signs, and readiness to address potential complications (Yaya et al., 2019). A woman who is pregnant for the first time or delivered the last pregnancy through caesarean section will be eager and ready to make adequate preparation towards the delivery of her baby than those who have not encountered any complication during delivery. This is also true for those who have experienced obstetric emergencies such as ante partum and post-partum hemorrhage pre-eclampsia, prolonged labor etc in their previous pregnancies as they will do everything possible to prevent them from reoccurring by practicing birth preparedness.

Education empower women with knowledge to make informed decision. Furthermore, educated women are better equipped to recognize danger signs and symptoms of potential complications during pregnancy and childbirth (Sakeah et al., 2014). Their ability to interpret health-related information enables them to differentiate between normal physiological changes and signs that warrant immediate medical attention. This heightened awareness contributes to effective complication readiness, as educated women are more likely to identify emerging challenges and seek timely medical assistance (Kuo et al., 2014). Onasoga et al., (2016) stated that, women with lower levels of education may face barriers to accessing and comprehending health information, leading to potential gaps in birth preparedness. Limited access to education can hinder their ability to access accurate and reliable health information, make informed decisions, and recognize danger signs. These barriers may result in delayed care-seeking and reduced readiness to address potential complications. Asefa (2022) reported that maternal education was a strong predictor in preparation for birth and complications and illiterate mothers were approximately five times less likely to be prepared for birth and complications than literate women. Another study by Saaka and Alhassan, (2021) confirmed this as he noted that high educational attainment of the woman and having adequate knowledge about obstetric danger signs during pregnancy were significant predictors of BP.

Knowledge is awareness gained through experience. Knowledge of the risk's factors associated with pregnancy and childbirth are correlated to their birth preparedness. Dessu et al., (2019) reported in their study that knowledge on danger signs of pregnancy were identified as independent factor that affect the birth preparedness of pregnant mothers. Ghimire et al., (2022) supported that having knowledge of obstetric danger signs is crucial to reduce maternal morbidity and mortality and this can be achieved by identifying the problems earlier and avoiding the delay in seeking obstetric care. Knowledge of obstetric signs can be acquired during the health talk in antenatal clinics.

The family's income level is a pivotal correlate of birth preparedness and complication readiness, exerting a significant influence on the resources available to ensure a safe and smooth childbirth experience. The economic stability and financial resources of a family directly impact their ability to access quality healthcare services, make informed decisions, and respond effectively to potential complications during childbirth (Shah et al., 2016). Families with higher income levels often have greater access to comprehensive antenatal care and skilled birth attendants. Adequate financial resources enable expectant mothers to attend regular prenatal check-ups, receive essential medical interventions, and benefit from the expertise of skilled healthcare professionals. This access to quality care enhances birth preparedness by addressing potential complications early, facilitating timely interventions, and reducing the risks associated with childbirth (World Bank, 2019). Conversely, families with lower income levels may face barriers to accessing essential maternal healthcare services. Financial constraints can limit their ability to afford resources needed to prepare for birth and complications.

Rivers South-East Senatorial District is uniquely patriarchal in nature with women being overburdened with reproductive health issues, majority of such women are also bread winners with so many engagements while carrying pregnancy with its attendant inconveniences. Yet, some of them have expressed their unexpectedness to labour onset, which deterred their preparation. Furthermore, most of these women patronize traditional birth attendants (TBA) who cannot render emergency obstetric care but contribute immensely to maternal and neonatal mortality. The gaps created by the poor maternal health seeking behavior in relation to birth preparedness affects the delivery of safe quality care during pregnancy, labour and postnatal period. It is a thing of worry that, despite the effort of the government in providing quality maternal healthcare services in the area by building more facilities and posting healthcare workers, women only come to such facilities when there are emergencies and they come unprepared. This necessitated this study to peruse the factors which linked to their birth readiness. Hence, this study investigated the correlates of birth preparedness among pregnant women in South-East Senatorial District, Rivers State. The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between family income level and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between parity and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between maternal educational status and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State?
4. What is the relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between family income level and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between parity and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between maternal educational status and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State.
4. There is no significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women attending antenatal care in South-East Senatorial District Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive correlational research design. The population of this study consisted of 1,965 women attending ante natal clinic in South East senatorial district of Rivers State (Primary HealthCare Board, 2023). The sample size for this study is 983 which is 50% of the entire population (1,965) because, when the population is a thousand or few thousand, 50% of the population can be used as the sample size. The data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire titled ‘Correlates of Birth Preparedness Questionnaire (BPQ).’ The instrument was adapted from the Johns Hopkins Initiative for International Education in Gynecology and Obstetrics (JHPIEGO) monitoring questionnaire for birth preparedness (2004). The reliability co-efficient of the instrument was 0.81 which certify the instrument to be reliable for use. Data collected were analyzed with the aid of the Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS V-23) using Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The guide for answering the research questions is as follow: 0.00-0.19 is very low, 0.20-0.39 is low, 0.40-0.59 moderate, 0.60-0.79 high and 0.80 above is very high.

RESULTS

Table 1: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between family income level and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District

Variables		BP/CR	Family income level	Decision
BP/CR	Pearson Correlation	1	0.26	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.	.	0.00*	
	N	969	969	
Family income level	Pearson Correlation	0.26	1	
	Sig.	0.00*	.	
	N	969	969	

*Significant; p<0.05.

Table 1 presents the Pearson Correlation analysis on significant relationship between family income level and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District. The result revealed that there was a significant low relationship between family income level and BP/CR as p<0.05 (n = 969; r = 0.26; p = 0.02). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between family income level and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between parity and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District

Variables		BP/CR	Parity	Decision
BP/CR	Pearson Correlation	1	0.28	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.	.	0.00*	
	N	969	969	
Parity	Pearson Correlation	0.28	1	
	Sig.	0.00*	.	
	N	969	969	

*Significant; p<0.05.

Table 2 presents the Pearson Correlation analysis on significant relationship between parity and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District. The result revealed that there was a significant low relationship between parity and BP/CR as p<0.05 (n = 969; r = 0.28; p = 0.02). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between parity and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between maternal educational status and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District

Variables		BP/CR	Maternal education	Decision
BP/CR	Pearson Correlation	1	0.13	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.	.	0.00*	
	N	969	969	
Maternal education	Pearson Correlation	0.13	1	
	Sig.	0.00*	.	
	N	969	969	

*Significant; p<0.05.

Table 3 presents the Pearson Correlation analysis on significant relationship between maternal educational status and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District. The result revealed that there was a significant low relationship between maternal educational status and BP/CR as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 969$; $r = 0.13$; $p = 0.02$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between maternal educational status and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District

Variables		BP/CR	Knowledge	Decision
BP/CR	Pearson Correlation	1	0.77	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.	.	0.00*	
	N	969	969	
Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	0.77	1	
	Sig.	0.00*	.	
	N	969	969	

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 4 presents the Pearson Correlation analysis on significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District. The result revealed that there was a significant high relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and BP/CR as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 969$; $r = 0.77$; $p = 0.02$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and BP/CR among pregnant women attending ANC in South-East Senatorial District was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The finding of this study showed that there was a significant relationship between family income level and birth preparedness/complication readiness ($n = 969$; $r = 0.26$; $p < 0.05$). The finding of this study is also expected because family's income level is pivotal to accessing quality healthcare services and respond effectively to childbirth demand requiring finance. Consequently, families with higher income levels may have greater access to comprehensive antenatal care and skilled birth attendants while low income may impede such access due to financial restrictions. By implication, adequate financial resources enable expectant mothers to attend regular prenatal check-ups, receive essential medical interventions, and benefit from the expertise of skilled healthcare professionals, aiding their adequate childbirth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Pervin et al., (2018) study on the determinants of birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women in a rural area in Bangladesh which showed that there was a significant relationship between family income and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study corroborates that of Gize et al., (2019) study on men's involvement in obstetrics care and birth preparedness/complication readiness in Burayu town administration, Oromia, Ethiopia which showed that there was a significant relationship between family income level and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study also corroborates that of Ananche and Wodajo (2020) study on birth preparedness/complication readiness and determinants among pregnant women in Ethiopia which revealed that there is a positive relationship between family income level and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The similarity between the previous studies and the present one might be attributed to the similarity in the study designs as they both adopted the descriptive research design.

The result revealed that there was a significant relationship between parity and birth preparedness/complication readiness ($n = 969$; $r = 0.28$; $p < 0.05$). This finding is anticipated because parity, which explains the number of children a woman has can be pivotal to her preparation for childbirth. By implication, some women who are delivering or just had one, might be more concerned

about the childbirth process and so be conscious to prepare adequate but those who have had more children, particular those without previous childbirth complications may be more relax and take it as, business as usual, no big deal so, may not be so conscious about it. The finding of this study is in keeping with that of Munkhondya et al., (2020) study on efficacy of companion-integrated childbirth preparation for childbirth fear, self-efficacy, and maternal support in primigravid women in Malawi, which revealed a significant relationship between parity and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The similarity between the previous studies and the present one might be attributed to the homogeneity of the study populations.

The finding of this study showed revealed that there was a significant relationship between maternal educational status and birth preparedness/complication readiness ($n = 969$; $r = 0.13$; $p < 0.05$). The finding of this is encouraging because empower women with knowledge to make informed decision and actively engage in their birth preparedness/complication readiness journey. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Pervin et al. (2018) study on the determinants of birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women in a rural area in Bangladesh which showed that there was a significant relationship between maternal educational status and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The result of this study also gives credence to that of Sialubanje et al. (2017) which showed that there was a significant relationship between maternal educational statu and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study corroborates that of Gize et al., (2019) study on men's involvement in obstetrics care and birth preparedness/complication readiness in Burayu town administration, Oromia, Ethiopia which showed that there was a significant relationship between maternal educational status and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study is in keeping with that of Worku *et al.* (2020) study on male involvement and associated factors in birth preparedness/complication readiness in Debre Berhan Town, North East Ethiopia revealed a significant relationship between women's educational status and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study also corroborates that of Ananche and Wodajo (2020) study on birth preparedness/complication readiness and determinants among pregnant women in Ethiopia which revealed that there is a positive relationship between maternal educational level and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The similarity between the previous studies and the present one might be attributed to the similarity in the study designs as they both adopted the descriptive research design.

The finding of this study showed that there was a significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness ($n = 969$; $r = 0.77$; $p < 0.05$). The finding of this study is anticipated because having knowledge of obstetric danger signs help women to identify any problem earlier. By implication, when such danger signs are identified, it helps to focus on any area which may require special intervention and avert the consequences by preparing adequately and avoiding delay in seeking obstetric care. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Pervin et al., (2018) study on the determinants of birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women in a rural area in Bangladesh which showed that there was a significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study corroborates that of Gize et al., (2019) study on men's involvement in obstetrics care and birth preparedness/complication readiness in Burayu town administration, Oromia, Ethiopia which showed that there was a significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric emergency signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study is also in support of Dessu et al., (2019) whose report in their study revealed that knowledge on danger signs of pregnancy were identified as independent factor that affect the birth preparedness/complication readiness of pregnant mothers. The finding of this study is also akin to that of Ghimire et al. (2022) that having knowledge of obstetric danger signs is a predictor to birth preparedness/complication readiness and avoiding the delay in seeking obstetric care.

The result of this study is in consonance with that of Ayele et al., (2019) whose study on utilization of skilled birth attendant at birth and associated factors among women who gave birth in the last 24 months preceding the survey in Gura Dhamole Woreda, Bale zone, southeast Ethiopia revealed a significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric danger signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness.

The finding of this study is in keeping with that of Worku et al., (2020) study on male involvement and associated factors in birth preparedness/complication readiness in Debre Berhan Town, North East Ethiopia revealed a significant relationship between knowledge of obstetrics danger signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness. utilization of skilled birth attendant at birth and associated factors among women who gave birth in the last 24 months preceding the survey in Gura Dhamole Woreda, Bale zone, southeast Ethiopia revealed a significant relationship between knowledge of obstetric danger signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The finding of this study also corroborates that of Ananche and Wodajo (2020) study on birth preparedness/complication readiness and determinants among pregnant women in Ethiopia which revealed that there is a positive relationship between knowledge of obstetric danger signs and birth preparedness/complication readiness. The similarity between the previous studies and the present one might be attributed to the similarity in the study designs as they both adopted the descriptive research design.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, birth preparedness/complication readiness among pregnant women in South-East Senatorial District, Rivers State was correlated with the socio-demographic factors of women such as family income level, parity, maternal educational status and knowledge of obstetric emergency signs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The ministry of health through the help of the government with funding should make provision for free delivery materials needed by women, this will help to ease the influence of income on birth preparedness and complication readiness.
2. Government should make delivery in primary healthcare facilities subsidized, so that even women with higher parity will be prepared to visit there for delivery.
3. Governmental and non-governmental organizations should place more emphasis on female education to boost their educational level by establishing free adult females' educational centers.
4. Health educators in collaboration with nurses and midwives should enhance women's knowledge of obstetric emergency by visiting antenatal clinics at regular intervals to remind women on the need for adequate birth preparedness

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